
PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION WORKING COMPETENCES OF FUTURE EDUCATORS.

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Annotation

This article is devoted to ways to develop information skills among future teachers of preschool educational organizations. It examines the role and place of future educators in increasing the efficiency of the preschool education system in Uzbekistan.

Key words

preschool education, future teachers, information, competence, information competencies, material and technical base, education and training, pupil, creative approach, student, component.

Development of life in all spheres of life in Uzbekistan, the task of becoming one of the advanced democracies of the world and gaining its rightful place in the international arena was put into practice by the initiative and idea of President Sh. Mirziyoyev, the development of the country in the near future Special attention is paid to the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is being highly evaluated by foreign countries, the public, and influential experts as the main document on the way.

It involves expanding the network of preschool educational institutions, fundamentally improving the conditions in preschool educational institutions for the all-round intellectual, aesthetic and physical development of children, seriously increasing the inclusion of children in preschool education and ensuring its convenience, pedagogue and specific measures to improve the level of qualifications and ensure the effectiveness of specialists have been reflected. It should be noted that as the main part of the reforms implemented in all spheres in Uzbekistan, the education system, including the preschool education system, taking into account the best practices of developed countries and the latest achievements of science and modern methodology one of the main goals is to educate a perfect, well-rounded, intellectually developed person.

In order to implement the above, regulate relations, solve existing problems in the system, reform preschool education, and improve it further, in the last five years, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the system, the Decree and Decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan The decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic were adopted. In order to ensure the implementation of legal and regulatory documents adopted by the government, based on the relevant orders of the Ministry of School and Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, state requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan, preschool education staff documents such as qualification descriptions of the main positions, work documents of pedagogues of state preschool education organizations were approved. The adoption of decrees, decisions and orders related to the field, literally, taking into account the interests, abilities, unique personal, mental and physical characteristics, spiritual needs of children of preschool age and the child's mental, physical, spiritual started a completely new formation of a holistic process aimed at all-round development, taking into account the formation of skills, the acquisition of life and social experience.

Increasing the effectiveness of the preschool education system, in turn, depends on its material and technical base, the level of provision of qualified pedagogic personnel, the use of modern educational programs and science-based theory in the educational process, created for the comprehensive development of children. taking into account the conditionality, on December 29, 2016, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021 was signed [3]. As a result, the quality of pre-school education and preparation of children for school has been radically improved through the development and implementation of alternative programs.

Ensuring the implementation of the decision, as one of the main priorities of the state policy, continued the reforms in the continuous education system of our republic, ensured its gradual progress as an integral part of its development.

On December 16, 2019, for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, a separate and most important document related to the field, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Training" [1] was adopted. In this law, in addition to regulating all relations in the field of preschool education and upbringing, it is a type of continuous education aimed at developing children spiritually and morally, ethically, aesthetically and physically, as well as preparing children for general secondary education. was recognized. (Article 3 of the Law).

In our country, raising the preschool education system to a new level, taking into account the improvement of the quality of pedagogues based on advanced international standards, special attention is paid to the professional standards of pedagogues in the system. This issue is reflected in the Law "On Preschool Education ". Including Law Article 42 mentions one of its important aspects - "Professional standard of the pedagogue" [1] . According to it, the application of the standard determines the requirements for the personal qualities of the pedagogue , which are inseparable from his knowledge, skills and abilities. The qualification of the pedagogue The provision of the category according to this standard was confirmed by this article.

Activities necessary for the student in the future, to prepare children's growing personality for life, to develop moral standards and national, family, personal values, to interact with others, to solve tasks related to communication means that he should have certain competence to ensure the formation of methods.

Competencies reflect a coherent set of knowledge, skills and abilities, as well as motivation to act independently based on acquired values. A competent pedagogue can perform professional duties effectively and qualitatively. Modern competence includes not only competence, knowledge and skills, but also the following values and moral qualities.

The student should have a holistic approach to his development and upbringing, taking into account the decisive importance of the early period in his professional activity, in the formation of the child based on his uniqueness;

ensure integration in education in determining, planning and developing the main goals of preschool education;

defines the need for children to have competencies such as strong cooperation with their families, making joint decisions in cooperation by involving parents in the activities of the preschool educational institution.

is often analyzed in the pages of scientific literature . However, the rapid development of the information society shows that it is not appropriate to simply associate information competence with computer literacy, but requires a deep and detailed analysis of this issue.

A creative approach can be used to determine competence. Competence of a highly educated educator is creative (productive) personal qualities (knowledge, skills, experience, personal virtues, etc.) can be defined as action and ability (readiness) to perform in the activity.

Information competence is a concept that needs to be clarified in the period of modern development of pedagogy. Some researchers define "information competence"

as "new literacy", which includes the ability to make fundamentally new decisions using technical means in emergency situations, and the ability to independently and actively process information by a person [55; 32 b].

Researchers refer to information competence as a type of "personal integrative qualities" specific to a particular domain of knowledge, which includes the processes of selecting, assimilating, processing, and transforming information, which help to make optimal decisions, hypothesize and implement in various aspects of activity. evaluated [147], while another researchers " Information competences are individual activity abilities and qualities that determine the following opportunities and skills: independently search for information, collect, analyze, present, transfer, etc. states that it includes" [107]. Some researchers, in their work, show the information competence of an educator as a special type of knowledge that can correctly assess the situation using new information technologies and make effective decisions in their professional and pedagogical activities.

Information competence is considered an effective, constructive process of information activity (external and internal) based on computer literacy, and is evaluated by the ability to effectively use knowledge in solving the problem facing a person. A literate person has an abstract idea about something, and a competent person can accurately and effectively solve an informational issue or problem in his professional field based on his acquired knowledge. At the same time, competence means avoiding direct copying of foreign experience, norms, traditions, examples, someone's assignments, instructions.

In the conditions of the modernization of education, while the main task is to ensure its development, one of the main resources of such development is the person who is able to work in the conditions of changes, to be the subject of reforms in education. is a pedagogue-educator. The position of the teacher, his educational functions will change radically, the demand for his professional skills and professional competence will increase.

The student's information competence is manifested in technological thinking and refers to the aspects of analytical, projective, predictive, reflexive ability and application of information in pedagogical activity. In addition, information competence is considered a component of the student's information and technological culture, performs integrative functions, serves as a link connecting general pedagogical and special knowledge and skills.

The student's information competence can be presented through the following chain of actions:

- feeling the need for information;

- developing a search strategy, that is, formulating a request and selecting information sources;
- evaluation of information;
- synthesis;
- effective use of new information resources and implementation of professional activities at the reproductive and creative levels.

The student 's information competence is manifested in :

- to be attentive to the information available in various sources, to be constantly interested in information activities;

- to have the ability to clearly formulate one's information requests;

- to use various information, to consciously choose them, to manage them;

- ability to orient the flow of information and it can freely use and manage its benefits;

- knowledge and wide use of information search algorithm (technology) in professional activity;

know how to open and close information, process it during use, bring it into the system, create new information;

- knowledge of creating, storing and distributing information.

This view can be said to be one of the efforts to interpret information competence as qualities that systematically develop the professional competence of a modern teacher. But not all of the mentioned elements are considered important aspects of the educator's informational and pedagogical competence (gnostic, projective, constructive, communicative, etc.).

Information competence is defined as one of the important competences of a person who can work with information in any form, understand one's place in the information environment, values, knowledge, skills, competences, and abilities, and all this is the use of information resources and it is possible to come to the end of creating them, performing professional activities on a reproductive and creative level.

We try to reveal the following functions of information competence:

Information function that requires the modernization of the content of student training, relying on information activities.

Gnesological (cognitive) consists in the fact that the student, in the process of information activity, brings his knowledge about information into the system. This function focuses on the student's ability to understand his knowledge and self-awareness in the process of using information resources in his professional activity. The student understands himself and his capabilities during information activities.

Implementation of the gnesological function develops the student's emotional-valuable attitude to information, self-determination of the value of the received information.

The communicative function is manifested in the semantic component, which displays information on paper (textbook, study guide, etc.) and electronic (electronic textbook, e-books, etc.) carriers. Communicative function becomes concrete according to the level of the student's mastery of the principles of cooperation in the organization of information activities, the ability to create conditions for creativity and self-realization of the individual in the process of forming information competence.

Constructive function implies that the student plans and develops information activities in the material of his professional activity.

The integrative function is manifested in the influence of many factors on a person, in the student's compliance with moral and professional values, which are developed in the educational society, are adequate to the goals of this educational process. The idea of "environment of opportunities" is realized for all participants of the educational process: the efforts of the entire educational community are united in order to find solutions to the problems faced by modern education. Integrative function, integration of information content, information competence of the student 's educational activity is manifested at the level of optimization.

The organizational function is implemented on the basis of the student's ability to choose the optimal methods of organizing his information activity in order to develop pedagogical information competence. Knowing how to use and apply information for a student plays an important role in determining the direction vector of information activity, which helps the student adapt to life conditions and activities in the information society. The essence of this function is that it serves to form and activate the student's ability to orientate in the flow of various information, to search for and choose known and new ones, to evaluate important and secondary ones.

Developmental function. All the functions mentioned above are united and subordinated to it. This is not only about mastering and using the system of special knowledge, norms, and rules in today's information society, but also about the formation of active independent and creative research that leads to self-expression and activation of the subject. . Developmental function aimed at the active independent and creative research of the subject (student), the student's use of professionally important information, intelligence, skills and abilities, development of professional activity, perception of professionally necessary information, is an important factor in understanding and use.

Relying on the approach of a number of researchers, we distinguished the informational, gnesological, communicative, constructive, integrative, organizational, developmental functions of students' information competence.

According to some researchers, the characteristics of the "Information competence" category are as follows [147].

- dualism - existence of objective (external assessment of information competence) and subjective (internal - assessment of information competence by the individual) sides.

- relativity - knowledge and the base of knowledge quickly become outdated, and this knowledge can be seen as new only in a conditional way, in the context of a specific environment.

- structure - the fact that any person has a knowledge base organized in a particular situation.

- selectivity - not all information entering the organized knowledge base becomes knowledge.

- accumulation - after a certain time, the base of knowledge and knowledge tends to "accumulate" - accumulation, become wider, deeper, voluminous.

- self-organization-spontaneous emergence of separate structures of the new knowledge base.

- multifunctionality - information on various topics the presence of a base (the semantic competence base of knowledge is considered multifunctional).

Agreeing with the opinion of the researchers, we determined the characteristics of dualism, relativity, structuredness, selectiveness, accumulation, self-organization, multifunctionality of the category of information competence.

The teacher-scientist DV Golubin, in his research, formed a unique view of the structure of information competence of the educator. These are:

1. Social competence: interaction with colleagues and students using information technologies; availability of abilities, knowledge and skills, as well as management skills in the formation of information culture among students; ability to work and cooperate with students in a group in an information environment.

2. Special competence: synthesis of knowledge in the field of taught science, teaching and knowledge methodology in the field of informatization of pedagogical activity; having the ability to work with various sources of information, methods of its processing; application of teaching methods and methods using modern computer programs; organization of the pedagogical process using information technologies.

3. Individual competence: readiness for informatization of pedagogical activity, need for it; abilities (informative thinking, reflection, self-assessment, stability of

emotions, professional position, etc.); individual style of information behavior; readiness for self-improvement and self-awareness in the field of informatization of pedagogical activities.

4. Personal competence: understanding the importance and significance of information for pedagogical activity; valuable attitude to information resources and new information technologies, their use; constant interest in the problems of informing pedagogical activities, solving them, self-development of a person in his professional activity [26; 192].

Based on the scientific conclusions of the scientists of the field, considering different views on the structure of information competence of students, we distinguish the following components: cognitive, motivational-value, organizational-activity, reflexive.

The cognitive component reflects knowledge of theoretical and technological nature, information activities, reception methods, information processing and storage, new knowledge formation methods, capabilities and limitations of information processing technological tools.

The motivational-values component includes the reasons, purpose, needs, and self-development of education. It refers to the interest in information activities, the person's need for knowledge, the ability to acquire effective methods of organizing information activities, as well as the person's readiness to implement them.

The organizational activity component implies the ability to use information technology tools, skills, and experience. Creative activity includes the experience of describing problems, choosing and using appropriate tools to solve them.

This component consists of communicative and organizational types of activity. Communicative activity is aimed at establishing interpersonal relations. The student's organizational activity includes both collaborative and individual activities.

The student's activity includes the organizational activity component, consulting, counseling, project, program discussion, participation in the organization of collaborative projects, scientific conference, report in pedagogical councils, and participation with a lecture.

In the structure of information competence, we have identified a reflexive component. This component helps to determine the level of respect for the individual, his responsibility for the results of his information activities, self-awareness in his pedagogical activities. The reflexive component manifests itself in the implementation of information activities, in its preparatory abilities.

of competences in the field of preschool pedagogy, which are able to develop, educate and implement educational functions of preschool education in the future. ,

refers to an educator who has the methodology of teaching and educating children of preschool age.

The teacher should try to use the personal computer and other information technology tools more widely, taking into account the various aspects of their use.

During his research on CoHa, researcher A. Karshiev wrote "Electronic education and distance learning "The implementation of educational technology requires a high level of independence and responsibility from students and teachers, as well as improved competence in working with technology" [115; 98-107 b].

The student's competences in working with information imply the wide use of computer technologies, electronic versions of educational literature, teaching programs, and pedagogical technologies of a creative nature. In the future, the student should have the necessary training to correctly differentiate the students in the groups, regardless of their individual aspects, motivation, age and psychological characteristics.

Thus, considering the aspects of the structure and content of the competences of students in working with information, it is defined as the ability to effectively work with information in any form, which represents the generality of knowledge, skills, and abilities, who knows his place in the information environment, who knows his place in the information environment as a set of norms related to the use and creation of resources, as values, can be defined as one of the most important human competencies that perform professional activities at the reproductive and creative levels.

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